

Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines Compliance with the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018

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Abstract: This study evaluated the Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines' (CAAP) compliance with Republic Act No. 11032, also known as the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018. The study involved thirty-two (32) participants, comprising of twenty-two (22) CAAP employees, including office or administrative assistants, compliance officers, information officers, medical personnel, airmen examiners, accounting and collection personnel assigned in different offices that handle clients and ten (10) aviation stakeholders including pilots, examinees and liaison officers who availed the services of CAAP.

The study employed the quantitative research method. Quantitative research involved the collection and analysis of numerical data to provide answers to the research questions. For the research design, this study used a descriptive design employing a cross-sectional survey. The survey was conducted at the Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines (CAAP). Convenient random sampling ensured a representative sample from CAAP and its clients. The primary data collection tool was a survey questionnaire designed based on the research questions. Data collected from the survey were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Frequency and Percentage provided data on the participants' profiles that were relevant to the information the researcher deemed important to obtain. The percentage method was utilized to arrive at an accurate estimate of the participation rate. Weighted Mean was used to calculate the average frequency of the responses. A four-point Likert Scale was used to determine the compliance of CAAP with the requirements of the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018.

Furthermore, Kruskal-Wallis H Test was used to determine if there was a significant difference in the participant's adherence to CAAP's compliance with the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018 requirements when grouped by age and length of service. The Mann-Whitney U Test was used to determine the significant difference in the participant's adherence to CAAP's compliance with the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018 requirements when grouped by gender and occupation. Lastly, ranking was used to prioritize and rank the factors, aspects or variables identified in the study.

The study revealed a relatively young workforce within CAAP, potentially influencing their familiarity with digital processes and government service expectations. Gender distribution was balanced, with more male participants. Most participants were government employees, reflecting the prevalence of public sector workers. The length of service varied, providing diverse perspectives on the implementation of the Act.

Key findings included room for improvement in the Citizen's Charter, unclear utilization of Public Assistance Desks which are vital in government agencies, adherence to standard government service delivery, and issues with the Zero Contact Policy that limits the interaction between the processor and the client. Significant age-related differences were observed in Citizen's Charter compliance, while gender and occupation showed no significant differences.

The challenges encountered by CAAP in aligning its procedures based on the Act, included adapting to evolving technology and industry regulations and cultural and organizational barriers. These challenges raised by the participants were timely and relevant since government procedures and guidelines continue to improve and evolve over the years. Internal procedures and office policies should be reviewed and monitored to ensure compliance with all government laws and regulations.

The recommendations included age-sensitive engagement strategies that would cater to diverse age groups, establishing a Public Assistance/Complaint Desk tasked with the sole purpose of providing assistance to the stakeholders, implementing the Zero Contact Policy to limit interaction and avoid red tape, and prioritizing automation to streamline procedures and enhance customer service delivery.

1. THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Introduction

"The Future is in the Skies" serves as the inspirational motto of the Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines (CAAP), prominently displayed on their website and within the corridors and elevators of their offices. This mantra underscores the aviation sector's pivotal role in our nation, serving as a cornerstone of transportation and tourism, and contributing significantly to our economic advancement. Each passing year witnesses a growing number of individuals taking to the skies to explore new destinations and create lasting memories. As the Philippines strives to recover from the far-reaching impacts of the pandemic, which have left a substantial mark on the transportation and tourism sectors, CAAP stands as one of many government agencies working diligently to get back on track and provide enhanced services to the traveling public.

Established through Republic Act No. 9497, passed on March 4, 2008, CAAP's core mission is to ensure the provision of safe and competent air transport services and regulatory oversight within the country. It was created to facilitate the reorganization of the civil aviation structure and to oversee the advancement, growth, and supervision of various operational, safety, and aviation security functions under its purview.

The inception of CAAP in 2008 marked a significant milestone in a comprehensive civil aviation reform program initiated by the government. As an independent regulatory body, CAAP possesses quasi-judicial and quasi-legislative powers, functioning in tandem with the Department of Transportation (DOTr) to coordinate policies effectively.

Furthermore, CAAP operates as one of the government-owned and controlled corporations (GOCCs) supervised by the Governance Commission for the GOCCs (GCG). These GOCCs serve as vital tools for economic development, ensuring that their operations align with national development policies and programs.

To streamline and simplify government processes and reduce bureaucratic obstacles, Republic Act No. 9485 was enacted on June 2, 2007. This law was designed to eliminate corruption, define service standards for all transactions and make these standards transparent to clients. While it applied to both national and local government units, it exempted statutory and judicial functions.

The Anti-Red Tape Act categorized transactions as simple or complex, based on processing time, and imposed limits on the required signatures for specified documentary procedures. Notably, it introduced the Citizen's Charter, a vital component that mandated government service delivery offices to prominently display essential information. This information includes the applicable service procedures, responsible personnel for each step, maximum allowable processing times, document requirements, fees, and procedures for complaints and feedback.

In ensuring compliance with the Citizen's Charter, the CSC, Office of the Ombudsman, the Presidential Anti-Graft Commission, and the Development Academy of the Philippines were vested with authority to address infringements of the Act.

Republic Act No. 11032 or the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018, was passed on May 28, 2018, with the primary objective of simplifying requirements and measures to lessen bureaucratic obstacles and expedite government transactions, whether business-related or not. Section 30 of the Act mandated the ARTA, CSC, and the DTI, in partnership with other government agencies, to formulate the necessary guidelines and policies for law implementation.

All government agencies, including CAAP, that provide public amenities are mandated to conduct compliance cost analyses, perform appraisal studies, assess and expand their services, and engage in reengineering efforts as needed. These initiatives aimed to minimize bureaucratic red tape, reduce processing times, and foster greater efficiency and simplicity in public processes.

After a year, ARTA, CSC and DTI, in collaboration with other government agencies, promulgated the IRR of the law. This law is all-inclusive; it covers all government offices and agencies under the Executive Department, including local government units (LGUs), corporations that are owned or controlled by the government (GOCCs), and other government entities, domestically and internationally. Its reach encompasses both non-business and business-related transactions.

Background of the Study

The Republic must actively fight bribery and corruption while upholding honesty and integrity in public service, according to Article II, Section 27 of the Philippine Constitution.

Republic Act No. 11032, in line with this constitutional directive, seeks to promote honesty and accountability among public officials and employees. It also endeavors to enhance transparency in government transactions, encompassing the implementation of simplified requirements and processes to diminish bureaucratic hurdles and further government dealings, whether business-related or otherwise.

In the initial implementation of the Act, government agencies were mandated to expedite transactions particularly the release of permits and licenses. The responses from the government agencies were positive and transactions with the government became quicker and more convenient.

Setting a maximum time to respond to applications should result in significant efficiency gains. But in order for it to function, the first assessment had to be taken into account along with the necessary processing timeframe. Although ideal, if the required processing time based on the IRR does not account for the significant delays that may occur during the evaluation phase, it may be misleading.

Similar to other forms of legislation, the primary factor determining its success is the political determination to enact the law correctly and consistently. The stakeholders were shortchanged by a subpar assessment and reengineering of operating procedures. It appeared that RA 11032 would primarily help with administrative processes, like the issue of permits and public papers, despite its stated goals of making business easier and offering the public efficient government services. The stakeholders would regrettably have to control their expectations and look for other options as all other government service deadlines would have to fight with the infamous Filipino time delay.

Former ARTA Director General (DG) Jeremiah Belgica claimed in a Philippine Star article published on 05 September 2019, that despite increased efforts to stop illegal transactions in government offices, fixers are still widely available and continue to prey on Filipinos who want their documents released right away.

According to the report, DG Belgica stated that numerous government departments require capacity training in order to eliminate the need for fixers, in addition to establishing an Anti-Fixers Task Force. Dealing with fixers while obtaining papers from any government office carries legal ramifications.

In 2020, the World Bank ranked the Philippines 124th in terms of ease of doing business. Red tape and over-regulation have been the perennial problem in doing business in the country. For local businesses, it was a source of stress and an unnecessary obstacle that hindered productivity. The Philippines is only better within ASEAN than Cambodia, Myanmar and Laos.

In its capacity as the nation's civil aviation regulatory authority, CAAP has a fundamental obligation to ensure the availability of technically qualified personnel. It is tasked with the continuous update of its standards, systems, and procedures for civil aviation inspection, licensing, and oversight functions to align with the ideals laid down by the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) and other international aviation bodies.

Republic Act No. 11032 also applies to CAAP since it is a public organization with fiscal autonomy. This bill was an improved version of the Anti-Red Tape Act that aimed to improve the efficiency and speed of government transactions.

Since its establishment in 2008, CAAP has continually worked to streamline its processes concerning airmen examinations, issuance of licenses and permits, administration of medical examinations for aviation professionals, and other aviation-related procedures. Nevertheless, the agency's plans for automating its systems and processes have faced setbacks, primarily due to the disruption caused by the COVID-19 pandemic and constraints related to budget allocations from the National Government. The automation of CAAP's systems holds the potential to simplify, expedite, and enhance the convenience of its services for all stakeholders.

As an example, securing a Height Clearance Permit takes seven (7) working days to be released and every applicant would pay Php50 per application or structure. The requirements consist of seven (7) documents the applicant needs to prepare and submit to the Operational Safety Division of the Aerodrome Development and Management Service. From

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there, an initial assessment would be conducted. After the initial evaluation, the submitted documents would have to go through three other (3) offices for further evaluation and signing.

Such processes can be improved through automation of processes and digitalization of documents. Likewise, one of the requirements of the Act is the posting of the process flow for these transactions in conspicuous places where the stakeholders can see and read. However, transactions still get delayed due to internal factors such as complacency of personnel, limited staffing, multiple signatories, voluminous paper works in the offices and busy schedules of personnel-in-charge of assessment and approval.

A part of Republic Act No. 11032's requirements is establishing or creating a Public Assistance and Help Desk. There is an office assigned to function as an assistance and help desk, however, it is not the office's main function and the personnel assigned endorses the complaint, whether verbal or written, to another office, for proper handling. This practice makes the clients go through office-to-office to get updates or process their complaints / request.

In light of these circumstances, the researcher was compelled to undertake a study to evaluate CAAP's compliance with the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018.

Statement of the Problem

This study evaluates CAAP's compliance with the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio demographic profile of the participants in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender;
 - 1.3 Occupation; and
 - 1.4 Length of Service?
2. What is CAAP's adherence with the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018's requirements:
 - 2.1. Citizen's Charter;
 - 2.2. Access to Government Service through Frontline Services;
 - 2.3. Report Card Survey; and
 - 2.4. Zero Contact Policy?
3. What significant differences exist among participants' adherence to CAAP's compliance with the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018 requirements when grouped by demographic profile?
4. What challenges and barriers has CAAP encountered in aligning its practices with the mandates of the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018?
5. What recommendations can be proposed to enhance CAAP's compliance with the Act and streamline processes for improving overall service delivery?

Hypothesis

H₀ There is no significant difference that exists among participants' adherence to CAAP's compliance with the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018 requirements when grouped by demographic profile.

Conceptual Framework

The Conceptual Framework illustrates this study's framework which serves as the foundation upon which it was built. This study was based on the Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) of Republic Act No. 11032.

According to the IRR, the law was passed in accordance with and to further state policy, which aims to prevent graft and corruption in government, to promote integrity and accountability in government service, to foster proper management of public affairs and property, and to establish efficient practices for the timely turnaround of government service delivery.

The steps involved in obtaining a specific service, who is in charge of each step, what paperwork needs to be presented, and any payments that may be required are all outlined in the Citizen's Charter.

LGUs and all other government organizations must have a zero-contact policy. Unless such interaction is strictly necessary for the processing of the request or application, public officials and employees shall limit their interactions with the applicant or requesting party to the preliminary assessment and evaluation of the sufficiency of submitted requirements of an application or request.

Figure 1: Research Paradigm

The chief of the office or agency will be principally in charge of carrying out the Act's rules and regulations. He or she will be responsible to the general public for providing prompt, effective, practical, and trustworthy service. All procedures and transactions are considered to have been carried out with approval or consent from the highest authority overseeing the relevant government agency.

Significance of the Study

This study would render significance to the following:

The Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines (CAAP). This study would serve as an eye opener that they should improve their services and processes to better serve the public. This might be a tool in creating a one-stop shop for all the services the Authority is offering.

Aviation Stakeholders. This study would provide them with information on how their requests should be handled, the length of time involved in finishing a certain request process, and the office or person responsible for where they can follow up on their requests. They would be acquainted with the processes involved in CAAP which would help them understand the flow of communications within the Authority.

Other Government Agencies. This study would help them improve their own processes and adopt the best practices of CAAP in complying with the guidelines and policies of Republic Act No. 11032.

Nation Building and Promotion of Values. This study would be beneficial for nation building and promotion of values since it would cover government transactions and improve the efficiency of government agencies in delivering their services to the public. Values would be promoted as improving government processes entails a positive working environment for employees, thus providing better customer service to its stakeholders.

Future Researchers. This study could open possible topics for research that could be further studied and explored. They could also use this study as a reference for a similar topic or area of interest.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The main goal of this study was to determine how much the Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines (CAAP) complies with the rules set forth in the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018. The study would exclusively focus on gathering insights from CAAP's employees and stakeholders.

In accordance with the IRR of Republic Act No. 11032, this research examined CAAP's adherence to the requirements set forth by RA 11032. These requirements encompass the Citizen's Charter, Access to Government Service through Frontline Services, Report Card Survey, and Zero Contact Policy.

Additionally, the study delved into the challenges and barriers that CAAP has encountered in aligning its operational practices with the mandates outlined in the aforementioned law. Furthermore, it explored potential solutions and recommendations aimed at bolstering CAAP's compliance with the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018.

This research was conducted exclusively at the Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines (CAAP) Central Office, where all transactions, requests, and applications are assessed and approved.

This research focused on CAAP offices that primarily dealt with stakeholders such as the Aerodrome Development and Management Service, Airmen Examination Board, Office of the Flight Surgeon and Aviation Medicine, Business Development Division, Bids and Awards Committee, Central Records and Archives Division, Licensing and Certification Division, Flight Operations Department, Airworthiness Division, Accounting Division, Checking Section and Collection Unit.

The researcher also coordinated and sought the assistance and guidance of the CAAP Committee on Anti Red Tape Act (CART) whose main function is the Authority's full compliance with the Ease of Doing Business requirements and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018.

Definition of Terms

For the purpose of clarity and understanding, the following terms were defined as used in the study:

Anti-Red Tape Authority (ARTA). A government organization tasked with putting policies and procedures into action to simplify government procedures and cut down on bureaucratic red tape in order to increase efficiency and transparency in the provision of public services.

Autonomy. The capacity of an organization or entity to self-govern and make decisions independently without external interference or control.

Bureaucratic. The characteristics, processes, or practices associated with a bureaucratic system often involve complex administrative procedures and hierarchical structures.

Citizen's Charter. A declaration outlining citizens' obligations and rights when using public services. It also includes information about service standards, procedures, and feedback mechanisms to improve service delivery.

Civil Aviation. Encompasses all non-military aviation activities, including commercial and private air travel, as well as the regulation and oversight of air transportation.

Constitution. A foundational legal document that defines the parameters of a government, including its composition, authority, and people's rights.

Corruption. The abuse of power, typically for personal gain, through dishonest or unethical means. It can involve bribery, embezzlement, nepotism, or other forms of misconduct.

Cost Analysis. The examination and evaluation of expenses related to a particular activity, project, or program to determine its financial implications and efficiency.

COVID-19 Pandemic. A worldwide phenomenon caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus. It has led to widespread illness, social disruption, and significant global health and economic challenges.

Ease of Doing Business Law. Refers to the law that make it easier for businesses to operate, invest, and expand by streamlining and improving the regulatory environment.

Feedback Mechanism. A structured process for collecting and incorporating feedback from stakeholders or users to improve the quality of services or products.

Fiscal Autonomy. The degree of financial independence or self-sufficiency that an organization or government entity possesses, allowing it to manage its finances and resources independently.

Government-Owned and Controlled Corporation (GOCC). A business entity or corporation owned or controlled by the government, typically established to perform specific functions or provide public services.

Graft. The illegal acquisition of money, power, or advantages through corrupt practices, often involving the misuse of public office for personal gain.

International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO). A United Nations body tasked with creating and advancing global guidelines and standards for environmental preservation, efficiency, security, and safety in civil aviation.

Nation Building. The process of creating or bolstering a country's infrastructure, identity, and unity in order to support social progress and cohesiveness.

Process Flow. Represents the sequential steps or stages in a process, illustrating the order in which tasks or activities are carried out.

Public Affairs. The activities and communication efforts undertaken by organizations or government entities to engage with the public, manage perceptions, and promote understanding of their policies and initiatives.

Red Tape. The excessive bureaucracy and administrative procedures can impede efficiency and slow down processes within organizations or government agencies.

Report Card Survey. A feedback mechanism that collects and evaluates feedback from users or clients about the quality of services a government agency or organization provides.

Satisfaction Survey. A research methodology is employed to determine the degree of happiness or contentment that consumers have with respect to a particular experience, good, or service.

Time and Motion Studies. It involves systematically analyzing work processes and tasks to identify areas of inefficiency and improve productivity.

Zero Contact Policy. In the context of government services, aims to minimize or eliminate physical interactions between service providers and clients to reduce opportunities for corruption and enhance efficiency.

2. RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

The research design and methods to be applied in carrying out the study's methodology were described in this chapter. It contained the research design, study subjects, data collection tools and protocols, and the statistical analysis that would be performed.

Methods of Research

The study employed the quantitative research method. Numerical data was gathered and analyzed in order to test theories and respond to research questions. It was deemed appropriate for the study as it enabled the researcher to measure CAAP's compliance level with the requirements of the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018 and identify significant differences in compliance among participants when grouped by demographic profile.

For the research design, this study used a descriptive design employing a cross-sectional survey. The survey was conducted at the Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines, targeting administrative and office assistants, compliance officers, information officers, medical personnel, airmen examiners, accounting and collection personnel, and aviation stakeholders. Convenient random sampling would ensure a representative sample from CAAP and its clients. The primary data collection tool was a survey questionnaire designed based on the research questions. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the survey data. Descriptive statistics was used to summarize CAAP's compliance level with the requirements of the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018, while inferential statistics was used to test hypotheses and identify important factors affecting compliance.

Based on the findings, CAAP was able to identify the difficulties and impediments it had in bringing its procedures into conformity with the requirements of the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018, as well as suggestions to improve compliance and overall service delivery.

Participants of the Study

The study involved thirty-two (32) participants, comprising twenty-two (22) CAAP employees, including office or administrative assistants, compliance officers, information officers, medical personnel, airmen examiners, accounting and collection personnel assigned in different offices that handle clients, and (10) aviation stakeholders, including pilots, examinees, and liaison officers who availed the services of CAAP.

Validation of Instrument

With the help of specialists chosen for their knowledge and experience in the aviation sector, a content validation procedure was carried out to guarantee the validity and dependability of the survey questionnaire. The questionnaire was submitted for content validation to three experts: Atty. Godfrey Ragudo, Division Chief III and Vice Chairperson of the CAAP Committee on Anti-Red Tape (CART); Engr. Michael Makabenta of the Aerodrome Development and Management Service; and Atty. Frank Edward Marty, Assistant Director General I of the Flight Standards Inspectorate Service (FSIS). These experts were chosen for their expertise and experience in the implementation of Republic Act No. 11032. Their professional judgment and technical competence were instrumental in validating the contents of the data collection instrument.

A thorough examination and validation of the questionnaire were conducted to meet the validation objectives, ensuring the reliability and credibility of the research output in addressing the problem statement.

Data Gathering Instrument

A survey questionnaire served as the study's primary data collection tool. The problem statement and the research questions will serve as the foundation for creating the questionnaire. The survey was conducted among office or

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administrative assistants, compliance officers, information officers, medical personnel, airmen examiners, accounting and collection personnel assigned in different offices that handle clients, and aviation stakeholders who are pilots, examinees, and liaison officers availing CAAP's services.

The survey questionnaire consisted of closed-ended questions, with an option for participants to provide additional comments or recommendations. The questionnaire was divided into four (4) sections: (1) Demographic Profile, covering age, gender, occupation, and length of service; (2) CAAP's Adherence with the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018 Requirements; (3) Challenges and Barriers encountered by CAAP in aligning its practices with the mandates of RA 11032; and (4) Recommendations to enhance compliance and streamline processes for improving overall service delivery.

The survey questionnaire was made available online using Google Forms to ensure convenience and safety. Before starting the survey, participants were asked for their consent and given information about the study's design and methodology.

Statistical software was used to analyze the data. Descriptive statistics was used to examine the data, and inferential statistics was utilized to identify significant variations in participant compliance when grouped by demographic profile.

Statistical Treatment of Data

A spreadsheet contained all of the participants' data and information that was collected. The following statistical methods were applied in order to conclude the methodical and precise examination and interpretation of the data.

1. Frequency and Percentage. This technique provided data on the participants' profiles that are relevant to the information the researcher deems important to obtain. The percentage method was utilized to arrive at an accurate estimate of the participation rate. The formula to be used as shown below:

$$P = f / n \times 100$$

Where:

P = percentage

F = frequency

n = number of selected participants

2. Weighted Mean. Using this method, the average frequency of the responses was determined. The weighted mean was calculated using this method:

$$X = \Sigma fx / N$$

Where:

X = weighted mean

Σfx = total of the frequency

N = number of participants

Likert Scale. A four-point Likert Scale was used to determine the compliance of CAAP to ARTA's requirements. The interpretations were as follows:

Table 1: FOUR POINT LIKERT SCALE

OPTION	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating
4	3.25 – 4.00	Always
3	2.50 – 3.24	Sometimes
2	1.75 – 2.49	Seldom
1	1.00 – 1.74	Never

3. Kruskal-Wallis H Test.

If two or more groups of an independent variable have statistically significant differences on a continuous or ordinal dependent variable, it can be ascertained using this non-parametric, rank-based test. Another name for it was the "one-way ANOVA on ranks." With the participants categorized by age and length of service, the purpose of this test was to see if there was a significant difference in their adherence to CAAP's compliance with the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018.

$$H = \frac{12}{N(N+1)} \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{R_i^2}{n_i} - 3(N+1)$$

Where:

N = total number of values

R = the sum of the ranks for each sample

n with an i = the number in each sample

4. Mann-Whitney U Test. This assessment was employed to contrast variations between two separate groups in situations where the dependent variable is continuous or ordinal but not normally distributed. With the participants divided into gender and occupation, this test was utilized to find any significant differences in the participants' adherence to CAAP's compliance with the provisions of the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018.

$$U_1 = R_1 - \frac{n_1(n_1 + 1)}{2}$$

or

$$U_2 = R_2 - \frac{n_2(n_2 + 1)}{2}$$

Where:

R₁ = sum of the ranks in Group 1

R₂ = sum of the ranks in Group 2

n₁ = sample size for Group 1

n₂ = sample size for Group 2

U₁ = significant value for Group 1

U₂ = significant value for Group 2

5. Ranking. This technique represented the relationship between the objects in the set. It was used to prioritize and rank the factors, aspects, or variables identified in the study.

3. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter concisely overviews the study's findings, conclusions, and recommendations.

Summary of Findings

After collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data from the Survey Questionnaire, the study revealed the following noteworthy findings:

1. What is the demographic profile of the participants in terms of:

1.1 Age

Most of participants fall within the 31-40 years old age group (43.75%), followed closely by the 21-30 years old group (37.50%). This indicated a relatively young workforce within the sample, which could have implications for their familiarity with digital processes and expectations of government services.

1.2 Gender

The distribution is relatively balanced, with slightly more male participants (53.12%) than female participants (46.88%).

1.3 Occupation

A significant majority of the participants (68.75%) were government employees, highlighting the predominance of public sector workers in the study, which is highly relevant to the research topic.

1.4 Length of Service

A range of perspectives on the application of the Ease of Doing Business Act in terms of the employees' length of service distribution, showed a mix of more seasoned and relatively fresh workers. Implications included the need for tailored strategies to engage the young workforce effectively and continuous efforts to improve service delivery for all employees, irrespective of their gender or length of service.

2. What is CAAP's adherence with the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018 requirements:

2.1 Citizen's Charter

The lower rating for the procedure of filing a complaint implied that there might be room for improvement in this area to enhance users' transparency and ease of access.

It could be observed that the agency posts their Citizen's Charter (CC) in conspicuous places visible to its clientele and also on its website. The agency's goals, vision, mission, and fundamental values were all included in the CC. It also listed each transaction's maximum completion time, accountable party, required documentation, and step-by-step process. The Citizen's Charter was posted to give openness in government operations and to inform the public about the standards of service.

Although there was a comprehensive checklist of requirements for each type of transaction, one of the participants suggested updating the steps and the maximum time per transaction since manuals and processes were being updated every now and then.

The agency may need to focus more on tailoring its Citizen's Charter to meet the diverse needs and expectations of different age groups to enhance its compliance with the Act.

2.2 Access to Government Service through Frontline Services

The results showed that there was a Public Assistance Desk / Complaint Desk within the agency. However, most of the participants of the study were not familiar with the location of the desk and if it was being utilized for its purpose.

Additionally, although procedures might yet be improved, frontline services unmistakably adhere to the norm when providing government services. When an authorized signatory was away on official business, the workers would accept a written request from the requesting party with a substitute signatory. The offices were always attended even during lunch break.

However, denial of request was not properly communicated to the requesting party. According to the provisions of the Act, denial of request should be put into writing indicating the reason for such denial and the person denying the request. The agency should consider this provision since offices receive numerous requests and complaints daily.

2.3 Report Card Survey

The Report Card Survey measures the clientele's opinions regarding the effectiveness, sufficiency, and caliber of the agency's services. Its principal goal is to gather input regarding the agencies' adherence to the Citizen's Charter. It also seeks to rank the effectiveness of the agency and general client satisfaction.

The findings demonstrated that the requesting party was not charged any additional fees, and no one was proposing to expedite transactions in exchange for payment. This clearly exemplifies the agency's efforts to eradicate fixers in the

aviation industry. Similarly, each building had a visitor's logbook where stakeholders and visitors logged in. However, the physical set up of the office and service delivery could still be improved.

2.4 Zero Contact Policy

The objective of this regulation was to curtail the direct communication between processors and customers, which acts as a springboard for unscrupulous practices and bureaucratic red tape whenever a transaction needs to be completed quickly. The information acquired showed that the agency did not fully adhere to the Zero Contact Policy and that the processor had direct communication with the entity making the request.

3. What significant differences exist among participants' adherence to CAAP's compliance with the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018 requirements when grouped by demographic profile?

Age-wise, there were notable variations in the degrees of conformity with the Citizen's Charter between different age groups. The results, however, did not indicate any appreciable variations in compliance with respect to other standards, such as Zero Contact Policy, Report Card Survey, and Access to Government Frontline Services.

Regarding gender, there was no discernible variation in the degree of compliance between the male and female participants for each of the Act's four provisions.

Furthermore, individuals who worked for the government, especially in CAAP, and those who worked for private enterprises did not significantly differ in compliance levels.

Lastly, there was significant difference in the Report Card Survey according to length of service. This could be interpreted that CAAP might need to focus on complying with the Report Card Survey to meet the expectations of its employees and enhance its relationship with its stakeholders.

4. What challenges / barriers has CAAP encountered in aligning its practices with the mandates of the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018?

The results showed that one of the challenges that CAAP encountered in aligning its practices with the mandates of the Act is keeping up with the constantly evolving technology and industry regulations. Dealing with cultural and organizational barriers to implementing a more systematic processing of licenses, exams and claims was also identified as a challenge.

Manual processing of claims, payments, permits and licenses and inconsistent enforcement of regulations and standards were identified as barriers encountered by CAAP in aligning its practices with the mandates of the Act.

5. What recommendations can be proposed to enhance CAAP's compliance with the Act and streamline procedures for improving overall service delivery?

The implementation of tougher service levels in responding to complainants and passing complaints to offices was the top recommendation based on the results. Likewise, conduct of regular office audits and inspections to identify areas for improvement was also recommended by the participants.

Conclusions

The following conclusions have been drawn from the study's findings:

1. Most participants were government employees, and a significant proportion fell within the 21-40 years old age range, signifying a young workforce. While gender distribution is balanced, the length of service varies, with participants ranging from relatively new to more experienced employees.
2. The Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines is in compliance with the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018, which includes the Citizen's Charter, Access to Government Service through Frontline Services, and Report Card Survey. The agency did not observe the Zero Contact Policy, which restricts direct communication between processors and clients; instead, the processor had direct communication with the person making the request.

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3. There was significant difference in compliance levels among various age groups in the context of the Citizen's Charter. As for the other requirements, there were no significant differences in compliance across age groups. On the other hand, there were no significant differences in compliance levels in terms of the participants' gender and occupation. However, there is a significant difference in compliance levels for the Report Card Survey according to length of service.
4. Keeping up with the constantly evolving technology and industry regulations was the significant challenge that CAAP encountered in aligning its practices with the mandates of the Act. The significant barrier encountered by CAAP in aligning its practices with the mandates of the Act was the manual processing of claims, payments, permits and licenses.
5. The majority of participants suggested conducting routine office audits and inspections to pinpoint areas for improvement, as well as applying tougher service levels when responding to complainants who submit problems to offices.

Recommendations

These recommendations were made in light of the noteworthy results and conclusions of this study:

1. Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines (CAAP) should consider implementing age-sensitive strategies to engage and communicate with its relatively young workforce effectively. This could include targeted training programs, communication channels, and feedback mechanisms that resonate with the preferences of employees in the 21-40 years old age group.
2. The agency should put the Zero Contact Policy into effect. There should be a designated area or an established Business One Stop Shop (BOSS), a one stop business service where all documents, requests, applications and transactions will be received, initially assessed, endorsed and released.
3. CAAP may need to focus more on tailoring its Citizen's Charter to meet the diverse needs and expectations of different age demographics to enhance compliance with the Act.
4. CAAP should adopt and explore new technological advancements to expedite processing and release of licenses, payments and claims. Automation of CAAP's processes can greatly help in the fulfillment of transactions. The automation project hindered by the pandemic and limited budget should be prioritized to streamline procedures and enhance customer service.
5. Establish a Public Assistance / Complaint Desk whose primary goal is to handle stakeholder complaints and concerns in order to enforce a stricter service level when responding to complainants and passing problems to offices. CAAP should also conduct regular office audits and inspections to monitor compliance and identify areas that need improvement.